

A Cuban initiative for the implementation of pharmacogenomics in Latin America

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Abstract

Pharmacogenomics (PGx) seeks to elucidate interindividual variability in drug response, with the aim of optimizing therapeutic efficacy and minimizing adverse reactions. Although the field has gained scientific momentum in Latin America, its clinical implementation remains limited, largely restricted to academic settings. This short communication presents a regulatory framework—specifically, the Cuban pharmacogenomics guideline—as a foundation for regional implementation. This initiative proposes mapping existing regulations, identifying drug–gene pairs of high clinical impact, and developing a Latin American pharmacogenomic database to guide clinical practice. The Cuban guideline, the first of its kind in the region, covers biomarker validation, ethical considerations, and integration of PGx data into regulatory dossiers. The ultimate goal is to foster equitable, evidence-based personalized medicine in Latin America. Looking ahead, the hope is that personalized medicine will enable both doctors and patients to make more informed decisions about treatment options.

Keywords

pharmacogenetics, pharmacogenomics, personalized medicine, guidance

Pharmacogenomics (PGx) is essential for transitioning from population-based treatment to individualized therapy. Although clinical testing for selected genes known to influence drug efficacy and toxicity is increasingly available, discrepancies remain between biomarker data and their application in therapeutic recommendations (Kabani et al. 2023; Shugg et al. 2024).

As recently reported, successful collaborations are crucial for addressing PGx implementation challenges and associated ethical implications in global healthcare systems. The number of publications in PGx has consider-

ably increased, contributing to its progressive clinical integration (David et al. 2024). In this regard, the inclusion of pharmacogenomic information in FDA-approved drug labeling significantly facilitates the application of precision medicine (Mehta 2020).

However, for the successful integration of PGx into clinical practice, regulatory authorities must acknowledge its importance and actively participate in decision-making processes. They must also prioritize informed consent and ethical approvals for the responsible sharing and reuse of genetic and phenotypic data. Regulatory agencies

play a central role in translating PGx into clinical settings by defining the role of genomic data and promoting robust, scientifically sound clinical trials that meet regulatory standards. In this respect, agencies such as the U.S. FDA, Health Canada, the European Medicines Agency (EMA), and the Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices Agency (PMDA), along with the International Council on Harmonization (ICH), have issued various PGx-related guidance documents (Shekhani et al. 2020).

In Latin America, regulatory frameworks for PGx are still in their infancy. Notably, in April 2018, the Cuban regulatory authority (CECMED) published the “Guidelines for conducting pharmacogenomic studies during drug development” (CECMED 2018). To our knowledge, this represents the first formal PGx guideline in the region.

The Cuban guideline includes five key components:

1. Reception, coding, and storage of biological samples;
2. Use and validation of pharmacogenomic biomarkers;
3. Ethical considerations;
4. Clinical development with a focus on PGx integration into different trial phases;
5. Recommendation to include PGx information in the Summary of Product Characteristics (SmPC).

The procedural flow for incorporating PGx into drug development is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Flow chart of pharmacogenomic studies for drug development in Cuba.

The SmPC is a critical regulatory document providing healthcare professionals with evidence-based information on drug use. Currently, PGx data are included in the SmPCs of approximately 300 drugs approved by the European Commission, especially in oncology and drugs with narrow therapeutic indices. The FDA has implemented a similar approach (Zhou et al. 2024). These labels typically include genomic markers, functional variant descriptions, genotype-based dosing recommendations, and clinical actions. Recently, the Spanish Agency of Medicines and Health Products (AEMPS) launched a searchable database of PGx biomarkers in drug labels, facilitating their use within the public health system (Medscape 2023).

Despite such progress, discrepancies in recommendations across regulatory agencies hinder global PGx implementation. These inconsistencies are driven by scientific, ethical, legal, and economic factors, as well as variations in medical education, healthcare infrastructure, and access to genetic testing. Additional barriers include doubts about the clinical utility of PGx, lack of cost-effectiveness data, and limited inclusion of PGx in clinical guidelines and reimbursement systems.

To address these challenges in Latin America, we propose an initial strategy based on:

- Encouraging regulatory agencies to mandate the inclusion of validated genomic variants in the SmPC;
- Identifying the most frequently prescribed drugs and their associated biomarkers;
- Creating a regional PGx database containing drug ATC classification, key genomic variants, and SmPC-relevant information.

This approach would support clinicians in reducing adverse drug reactions and improving drug efficacy while aligning with regional health priorities.

Incorporating PGx in Latin America requires careful consideration of the region’s demographic and healthcare realities. The region is marked by ethnic diversity, heterogeneous healthcare systems, and reliance on medications developed and trialed in the U.S. and Europe. This leads to a mismatch between treatment regimens and population-specific drug response profiles. Solutions include:

- a. Multinational clinical trials that reflect regional diversity;
- b. Training of healthcare professionals in PGx;
- c. Implementation of genotype-based dosing algorithms tailored to local populations.

We identify the following critical challenges for PGx implementation in Latin America:

- Limited education and training among healthcare professionals, researchers, and regulators;
- Insufficient validation of testing procedures;
- Absence of interpretive frameworks for PGx results;
- Low awareness among clinicians about the clinical relevance of PGx;

- Lack of local cost-effectiveness studies;
- Weak or absent regulatory structures to support PGx testing;
- Few prospective studies validating clinical recommendations;
- Inadequate characterization of therapeutic failure or toxicity;
- Uncertainty around biomarker qualification and regulatory acceptance.

An additional yet often overlooked application of PGx is in post-marketing drug safety. Serious adverse drug reactions (ADRs) are among the leading causes of drug withdrawals and result in substantial economic burdens globally. Many of these ADRs could potentially be avoided through preemptive PGx testing. By identifying at-risk individuals based on genotype, pharmacogenomic screening can reduce the incidence of ADRs, improve diagnostic accuracy, and optimize treatment strategies (NewsMedical 2025).

Several important initiatives have been launched to promote PGx in Latin America. For example, the Ibero-American Network of Pharmacogenetics and Pharmacogenomics (RIBEF) fosters education and research across Spanish- and Portuguese-speaking countries. The Latin American Network for the Implementation and Validation of Pharmacogenomic Clinical Guidelines (RELIVAF) seeks to build a collaborative platform for the development of population-specific guidelines. Other contributing organizations include the Latin American Society of Pharmacogenomics and Personalized Medicine (SOLFA-GEM) and the Latin American Network for Human Genetics (RELAGH). Most recently, RELIVAF completed a comprehensive assessment of the current state of PGx implementation in the region (Salas-Hernández et al. 2023).

Conclusion

There is an urgent need to strengthen the genomic medicine infrastructure across Latin America. This will require the implementation of the WHO's recommendations on genomics and world health, including the development of regional academic and research partnerships, especially among Latin American countries. Capacity building in bioinformatics is equally critical to manage and interpret the growing volume of PGx data. Ethical, legal, and culturally appropriate frameworks must also be developed to ensure the equitable use of genomic technologies.

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Pharmacogenomics represents a powerful approach to enhancing therapeutic outcomes and addressing health-care disparities. Although the Cuban guideline is primarily aimed at integrating pharmacogenomics into clinical trials for drug development, it constitutes a pioneering effort that can serve as a regional model. By establishing harmonized regulatory frameworks, strengthening institutional capacities, and promoting collaborative networks, Latin America can move toward a more equitable, effective, and personalized healthcare system.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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